

on start
Start the code

Inclusive ER **01** micro:bit

on start

Runs to initialize the micro:bit

Used for initial settings (such as initializing values, clearing screen) and starting the program

forever
Continuously execute the code

Inclusive ER **02** micro:bit

forever

Continuously executes the set of commands placed inside the block

Used to continuously execute the main code we want the micro:bit to perform.

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

show number

Display a number on the micro: bit's LED screen

Inclusive ER

03

show number

Moves on the screen any number we put inside the circle

If the number we put inside the circle has more than one digit, each digit is moved on the screen separately

show leds

Display an image on the micro: bit's LED screen

Inclusive ER

04

show leds

Displays the image we want on the micro: bit screen

If, for example, we want a square to appear on the micro: bit screen, we select the appropriate LEDs in the block

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

show icon

Display an icon on micro:bit's LED screen

Inclusive ER

05

micro:bit

show icon ▾

Displays the selected icon on the micro:bit LED screen

show string

Display text on the micro:bit's LED screen

Inclusive ER

06

micro:bit

show string ○

Displays on the micro:bit screen the character we place inside the circle. If there are more than one character s, they appear on the screen one by one

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

clear screen

Turn off all the LEDs on the micro:bit screen

Inclusive ER

07

micro:bit

clear screen

Turns off all the LEDs from the micro:bit's screen. So, the screen is cleared of any code or graphics

pause (ms)

Pause the code by choosing a pause number

Inclusive ER

08

micro:bit

pause (ms) ○

Pauses the code for the time specified by the number inside the circle. Pause time is measured in milliseconds (ms)

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

on button pressed

Execute the code by pressing A or B or A+B

on button pressed ▾

Presses and releases the buttons A, B, A+B

When the A or B or A+B button is pressed and immediately released, the commands we have set are executed

Inclusive ER

09

micro:bit

on

Detects an action on the micro:bit

on ▾

Detects an action on the micro:bit

The action we want on the micro:bit is selected and then the commands we set are executed

Inclusive ER

10

micro:bit

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

on pin pressed

Press a pin on micro:bit

Inclusive ER

11

micro:bit

on pin ▼ pressed

The selected pin (P0, P1, P2) is pressed and released, executing the commands we have defined

button ▼ is pressed

Continuously pressing a button without releasing it

If one of the micro:bit buttons (A or B) has been pressed or both buttons at the same time (A + B), it executes the commands we have set

Inclusive ER

12

micro:bit

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half
2. Glue the backs together
3. Cut along the dashed line

light level

Find out how bright the place you are in is

light level

Inclusive ER

13

micro:bit

light level

Finds the light level of a place (how bright or dark it is)

light level

Light level 0 means a dark place and light level 255 means a place with intensive light

temperature (°C)

Receive the temperature of the place you are in

temperature (°C)

Inclusive ER

14

micro:bit

temperature (°C)

Receives the temperature of the place we are in (indoor or outdoor) and depicts it on the micro:bit. Temperature is measured in degrees Celsius (°C)

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half
2. Glue the backs together
3. Cut along the dashed line

on sound

Select the volume that the micro:bit will detect

Inclusive ER

15

on ▾ sound

Enables the microphone on the micro:bit.
Works with micro:bit v2 only

The microphone detects quiet or loud sound and executes the commands we have set

on logo

Select the action to detect the micro:bit logo and execute

Inclusive ER

16

on logo ▾

Enables the touch logo sensor on the micro:bit which acts like a touch button.
Works with micro:bit v2 only

The commands we want are executed when some action is detected on the touch logo sensor. Useful in touch-enabled environments (eg touch-screens)

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

music on

Select an action for the music tune

music on ▾

Checks the action we have selected for the music tune and if it is valid, executes the code

play

Play melody

play ▾ ▾

Plays the sound we select from the piano in a specific beat (1, 1/2, 1/4, ..., 4) and in a specific mode

- ### Make an iCard
1. Fold the card in half
 2. Glue the backs together
 3. Cut along the dashed line

plot x y

Turn on a specific LED on the micro:bit's screen

Inclusive ER

19

micro:bit

plot x ○ y ○

Turns on a specific LED on the micro:bit screen. The x and y coordinates take values from 0 to 4

Example: At position x=0, y=0 the top left LED turns on. This is because the coordinates are increasing to the right for x and downward for y

toggle x y

Toggle a specific LED on the micro:bit's screen

Inclusive ER

20

micro:bit

toggle x ○ y ○

Toggles a specific LED on the micro:bit's screen with the coordinates we have set for it

Example: At position x=1, y=4 toggles the specific LED shown in the picture

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

unplot x y

Turn off the LED on the micro:bit screen that is in a specific position

Inclusive ER

21

micro:bit

unplot x ○ y ○

Turns off the LED at the specific location on the micro:bit's screen, according to the coordinates we have set

plot bar graph of ○ up to ○

Displays a bar graph on the micro:bit's screen according to a ratio

The micro:bit's LEDs are 25. For example, if the max value is 10 and the numeric value is 6, then 16 LEDs will be light up

Inclusive ER

22

micro:bit

ΔΗΜΟΚΡΙΤΕΙΟ ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ ΘΡΑΚΗΣ DEMOCRITUS UNIVERSITY OF THRACE

IEES Lab

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

repeat times do

Repeat the code execution

Inclusive ER

23

micro:bit

repeat times do

Repeats the sequence of commands we have defined in the «repeats times do» block

For example, the commands defined inside the block will be repeated four times

while do

Repeat the code if the condition is valid

Inclusive ER

24

micro:bit

while do

Repeats the sequence of commands over and over again as long as the condition we have set is valid (true or false)

The condition is checked before any code is executed. This means that if the condition we specified is not valid, the sequence of commands inside the condition is not executed

Make an iCard

- 1. Fold the card in half
- 2. Glue the backs together
- 3. Cut along the dashed line

for from 0 to do

Execute an action for each value

Inclusive ER

25

micro:bit

for ▾ from 0 to ○ do

Executes the commands we want for as many times as we have defined inside the white circle, using a variable that counts the repetitions

every ms

Execute the code for a specified time

Inclusive ER

26

micro:bit

every ○ ms

Executes the commands we want over and over again for the time period we have set it

Similar to the "forever" block, except that there is an amount of time we set for it to wait before the commands are executed. Time is measured in milliseconds (ms)

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half
2. Glue the backs together
3. Cut along the dashed line

if then

Execute the code if the condition is valid

Inclusive ER

27

micro:bit

if then

Executes the commands we have defined, depending on whether a condition is true or false

The commands are executed only if the condition we have defined inside the block is valid

If then, else

Execute the code if condition is valid, else execute other code

Inclusive ER

28

micro:bit

if then, else

Executes the commands we have defined, depending on whether a condition is true or false

If the condition we define is valid, the commands inside the "if" block are executed. In case the condition is not valid, the commands defined in the "else" block are executed

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

comparison

Check if the values are equal

Inclusive ER

29

micro:bit

Compares the values placed inside the circles and checks if these values are equal

In addition, it has extra comparison options: \neq (different), $<$ (less than), \leq (less than or equal to), $>$ (greater than), \geq (greater than or equal to)

true

Set the condition true or false

Inclusive ER

30

micro:bit

true ▾

A value or condition can also be defined with a Boolean value (true or false). This Boolean value is checked and if it is valid, the commands we want are executed

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half
2. Glue the backs together
3. Cut along the dashed line

set to

Set a variable

set ▾ to ○

The variable we want is created to store some values. We can create as many as we want, modify them accordingly, or delete them

Inclusive ER **31** micro:bit

+

Calculate the addition of two values

○ + ▾ ○

Calculates the addition of two values inside the circles and executes the commands we want depending on the result

Accordingly, there is also the possibility of calculating the subtraction (-), the multiplication (*) and the division (/) of two values

Inclusive ER **32** micro:bit

- ## Make an iCard
1. Fold the card in half
 2. Glue the backs together
 3. Cut along the dashed line

pick random to

Randomly pick a number

pick random 0 to 10

Inclusive ER

33

micro:bit

pick random ○ to ○

The code picks a random number that is between the smallest (min) and largest (max) number we set inside the circles. The selection includes both the minimum and maximum value. Depending on the number selected, the corresponding commands we have defined are executed

pick random 0 to 10

Soil moisture sensor value(0 ~100)

Read the soil moisture

Soil moisture sensor J1 value(0~100)

Inclusive ER

34

micro:bit

Soil moisture sensor value(0 ~100)

Block from PLANETX extension. It measures the soil moisture value and stores it in the variable we defined before

The soil moisture sensor is connected to a port (J1 or J2) of the Nezha expansion board

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

Color sensor IIC port detects

Detect color

Inclusive ER 35 micro:bit

Color sensor IIC port detects ▾

Block from the PLANETX extension. It detects a color through a color sensor

The color sensor is connected to one of the three IIC (I²C) ports of the Nezha expansion board. The desired color is selected and when the sensor detects it, the commands we want are executed

Gesture sensor IIC port is ▾

Block from the PLANETX extension. It detects gesture through a gesture sensor

The gesture sensor is connected to one of the three IIC (I²C) ports of the Nezha expansion board, detecting various movements and executing the commands we want

Gesture sensor IIC port is

Detect gesture

Inclusive ER 36 micro:bit

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half

2. Glue the backs together

3. Cut along the dashed line

on button pressed

Press the button at the board position

Inclusive ER

37

micro:bit

On button ▾ ▾ pressed

Block from the PLANETX extension. A button is connected to one of the ports (J1, J2, J3, J4) of the Nezha expansion board and the commands we want are executed when this button is pressed

LED toggle to

Turn on or off the connected LED

Inclusive ER

38

micro:bit

LED ▾ toggle to

Block from PLANETX extension

A LED is connected to one of the ports (J1, J2, J3, J4) on the Nezha expansion board and we choose whether to turn it on, off or blink. Then the commands we want are executed according to our choice

Make an iCard

1. Fold the card in half
2. Glue the backs together
3. Cut along the dashed line